

Saturn: The Epitome Of Hard Work, Discipline, Honesty, Integrity And Spirituality: A Perspective

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ABSTRACT

Saturn, the son of Sun God and Chaya is the sixth planet in the solar system. The planet plays a pivotal role in both astronomy and astrology. However, this present paper attempts to showcase the scientific approach to ensure the cosmic equilibrium and the unfathomable impact it has on the human life, society and the nation at large during the chronic periods of Mahadasha, Dhaiya and Saresadi. The study explores the multiple domains of Saturn such as pains and sufferings, hard work, discipline, dedication, truthfulness, challenges, lessons and above all the eventual triumph and victory.

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Introduction

In the realm of Vedic astrology, Saturn holds an extremely holy position. Saturn is one of the coldest planets in the cosmic system as it is far away from the sun. Surrounded by a white ring structure, the planet really looks elegant when viewed through a telescope. Saturn is the embodiment of karma, justice, patience and above all discipline. The 'Graha Raj ' as mentioned in the sacred scriptures is dark skinned who rides a golden chariot dragged by Kalol, the crow, his one of the best companions. Shani symbolizes a slow but steady impact on the human life. Slow and steady always wins the race, despite all odds.

Objectives

As the Research Paper deals with a unique subject, there are certain objectives which would make the readers understand and analyse the 'real' truth behind this holistic approach.

First, it is quite important to understand the role played by the planet in the Vedic astrology and its influence on different houses of Kalpurush (the natural zodiac), the combinations that lead to the various auspicious and inauspicious yogas and the tough and stern periods of Dhaiya and Saresadi.

Secondly, Shani is a tough task master who has an unflinching affection for hardwork, discipline, endurance and karma. In fact such elements together shape the destiny of an individual.

Thirdly, over the years Saturn or Shani has been worshipped on Shani Jayanti and every Saturday as a part of rituals and practice to diminish the negative impacts.

Fourthly, the influence of Saturn is completely based on its position in one's personal natal chart. This presence is the result of our past and present actions.

And last but not the least, apart from the basic traits of Shani Dev there are other areas of art, science, literature and philosophy to interpret the concept of Saturn.

Scope and Relevance

The scope of this paper lies in the interpretation of Shani in various Hindi scriptures (such as Garuda Purana, Shani Mahatmya) to examine the source in different mythological texts, the rich symbolic attributes and the divine justice meted out to each and every creature of the cosmos. Moreover, the scope deals with the placement of Saturn, the straight and the retrograde motions, the combinations, the various forms of Dasha, Dhaiya and Saresadi. Infact such periods bring about a massive transformation in the human being with the tools of hardship, dedication and patience. As Shani has always laid a strong emphasis on Karma and not fortune, simple visits in the temple or following the rites and rituals to pacify Him won't serve the purpose.

On the other hand, the relevance of this particular issue includes the lessons the planet teaches in terms of career growth, stability and a sum total development. Besides, there are deep philosophical insights, beliefs, practices and challenges that often align with our psychological framework. Modern studies show the impact of Shani's 'Vakradristi' which breeds turbulence to create awareness. Jupiter, being the Guru cannot even intervene in his flawless sense of justice.

Methodology

This particular paper will follow a combined and structural study which combines the general backdrop and the astrological impact in the relevant sense of term. Moreover, the interpretation is made through the perception of karma and other metaphysical sources. A few real life studies, the modern day practice and above all the recent priority in the social media to transform life for a better future.

Role in the Cosmos

A look at the solar system reveals the strong gravitational pull of Saturn to ensure a perfect balance in the planetary orbits as well as the motion in the cosmos, which is always in the state of expansion. It is interesting to note that Shani takes a span of 29.5 years to complete one revolution. This further proves that Saturn takes the same span of time to arrive in that particular zodiac sign where it was 29.5 years ago. Moreover, the ice ring shows an immeasurable penchant for the strong boundaries of hardwork and discipline in every sphere of life.

The Vedic Perspective

The famed sage Parashar depicted the planet in terms of its nature and character. Being a slow moving planet, Saturn governs the areas of "human actions" and the subsequent results of our work.

Secondly, Saturn has a supreme control on time and the phases of life creating significant changes. Unlike Jupiter - the big, benign and benefic, Saturn teaches through hardships, delays and trials, leading each one of us to the ocean of spiritual expansion.

On the other hand, there are two houses of Saturn namely Makar (Capricorn) and Kumbh (Aquarius). Saturn rules and controls these houses. However, Saturn of Makar rashi loves to display materialistic pleasures and sacrifice in Kumbh. Kumbh rashi is the 'mool trikona' of Saturn - the happiest house of the planet. Saturn is exalted in Libra at (20 degree) , the house of Venus and debilitated in Aries , the house of Mars.

Symbolism

The following spheres are to be taken into account to discuss the symbolic aspects of the planet.

First, the dark complexion represents mystery, listlessness, karma, anguish, the true lessons, the motives of life and the reflection of past actions.

Secondly, his Vahanas which are either a crow or at times a vulture symbolize karma, destiny, endurance and a sharp insight. A complete detachment from materialism to seek the path of spiritual upliftment. Thus Rahu is the shadow planet of Shani, providing the same results and doesn't believe in destiny but karma.

And last but not the least his weapons Dhanda (the scimitar) reinforces the Karmic Laws, the sword slashes the illusions and falsehood to make everyone connect to the Supreme Reality. The Trident (Trishula) signifies the complete frame of time (past, present and future. He is the Trikal darshi like Lord Shiva who also holds a trident to represent the eternal cycle of time , inflicting pleasures and pains equally.

The Various Impacts: The phases of Mahadasha, Dhaiya and Saresadi

-According to Vedic astrology, the Mahadasha of Saturn or Shani is of nineteen years. During this period of time , an individual may have to face the Karmic justice, delays, detachment, isolation, loneliness and financial challenges. However, the result will not be the same for everyone. It depends on the placement of Saturn in the personal horoscope, the degree, the conjunction and above all the Nakshatra. Saturn's Mahadasha can also give huge success which one has not dreamt of, but after the various tests of life. On the other hand 'Dhaiya ', a period of two and a half years create a considerable impact on an individual. Dhaiya is a phase when Saturn is placed fourth from the moon. It is also known as Kantak Shani. The period is replete with disturbance, property and vehicle related issues, conflicts at the work station, unusual stress and health problems of mother, loneliness, stress. Besides, if Saturn is placed in the eighth house from moon, it is called Astama Shani which dictates delays, disturbances, financial constraints, accidents, surgeries, spiritual awakening, hidden enemies and betrays. However, it is to be noted that if the fourth and the eighth house belong to his own or friend's house or equal house , the impact will be balanced.

Focusing on Saresadi is an important section of this paper. A period of seven and a half years. The period begins when Shani comes in the twelfth house of a particular zodiac. This is known as the ' Rising Phase" and continues for two and a half years. The second phase also known as the " Peak Phase" takes place when Shani or Saturn transits over the moon. This also continues for two and a

half years. Finally the third or the "Setting Phase" begins as Shani or Saturn transits to the second house from the moon. The same span of time, but a gradual phase of relief sets in. However the results differ from one case to another. Let us have a look:

First phase: Health issues, operation, loneliness, huge loss, foreign travel, sleep issues.

Second phase : Afflicting health, disturbance in relationship, emotional stress, financial crush, depression, mood swing, huge success, recognition, notable communication skills, personal and spiritual expansion. A test of patience and resilience.

Third phase : A gradual feel of relief, new opportunities are seen. A gradual improvement in relationship, friendship, finance and health.

Remedial Measures

Though good karma or actions is the best remedy, certain other remedial measures have come up to pacify the wrath and cruelty of Saturn. They chiefly comprise worshipping of Mahadev, seeing one's face in a bowl of mustard oil and then offering that oil to the temple of Shani, visiting his temple on Saturday and offering white garland and flowers to him and lighting clay lamps before a Peepal tree.

The Spiritual Lessons

First, no matter if the action is good or bad embrace it.

Secondly, the reward is always based on the fusion of past and present actions.

Thirdly, always be practically truthful and never complain about the situation you are put into.

Fourthly, true justice is not always about punishment. It is rather about balance and corrections.

Fifthly, true happiness lies in self contentment, breaking the walls of illusion and embracing simplicity.

Sixthly, there is no short cut to success. Keep the faith on the Supreme Lord for an honest growth, success, triumph, mental strength, grace and clarity.

Finally it is to be noted that after the period of Saresadi, there is a radical transformation in the individual, making him or her an icon before others.

Conclusion

Undoubtedly toughness, harshness, punishment are essential for maturity, wisdom and liberation. Embracing humility, humbleness, patience ensures stability, success, happiness, prosperity and enlightenment.

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